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ALMeD: Medieval French Gold-Standard

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Abstract

Medieval French is one of the Romance vernacular languages with a significant history of transmission and an enormous influence on other vernacular languages of the time. The sources convey valuable knowledge about all aspects of culture. The study of Medieval French has, over the last few years, increasingly benefited from NLP-based methods. There have been numerous efforts to parse medieval French; however, these efforts use corpora comprising legal texts and—primarily—literary texts as their foundation and training data. This means that, except for juridical resources, **scientific literature** is overlooked. We present **ALMeD**¹, an annotated, semantically rich corpus (work-in-progress) of medical and surgical treatises produced in medieval French, i.e., Old and Middle French, including **Anglo-Norman**. Our **semantically disambiguated gold-standard** goes beyond existing resources, focusing on **medical terminology**, and accounts for morphological development, evolving syntactical structures and lack of spelling normalisation in these languages.

1 Introduction

Natural Language Processing (NLP) for historical language stages remains a niche area of research, due to the lack of resources and challenges caused by non-standard syntax and spelling, among others. Nevertheless, recent years have seen a growing number of initiatives, such as Universal Dependencies and various efforts within the Digital Humanities for various languages like Ancient Greek, Latin, Classical Chinese, and Ancient Hebrew. However, there are still major issues, such as the scarcity of high-quality training data, especially gold-standard annotated corpora; difficulties in contextualising information accurately; and issues such as model hallucination.

¹A first version is available at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/HaDW-ALMA/ALMeD>.

One such language that suffers from these issues is Medieval French — a broad categorisation that includes Old French and Middle French. Old French in itself refers to a group of language varieties spoken primarily in Northern France from around the 9th Century until the middle of the 14th Century, and followed by the Middle French language period, which lasted until circa 1500.

The rise of textual culture and new educational institutions in Medieval cities led to the emergence of new expert groups and methods of knowledge generation and transmission, fostering the use of vernacular languages, including Old French (and other Old Gallo-Romance languages such as Old Occitan, as well as Old Italo-Romance language varieties) as a form of written communication. While (Middle) Latin remained dominant in administration, education, and scholarship for a long time, vernaculars began to play an increasingly important role — albeit in regionally varied ways — often still dependent on Latin models.

This linguistic shift was gradual and uneven, reflecting deeper socio-cultural transformations. The adoption of vernaculars for conveying knowledge changed intellectual networks and signalled a broader renewal of the intellectual landscape, contributing to the development of Europe as a knowledge society. The conceptual development of these languages both reflected and drove social change, forming a crucial part of Europe’s cultural and scientific heritage.

Within the Romance vernaculars, Medieval French was a dominant medium of cultural life, encompassing not only literature but also art and architecture, technical developments and medicine, amongst other things. The prestige of French in the medieval world is directly reflected in the number of text witnesses from Northern France, England, the Holy Land, etc. The textual tradition comprises many thousands of texts. This makes developing NLP-supported approaches to analysing Medieval

French texts — for philological, linguistic, and cultural-historical research questions — crucial.

However, although some NLP tools already exist for Old French — such as the *Stanford CoreNLP* model, the *Pyrrha* project (Clérice, 2018) by the École Nationale des Chartes, and the *Syntactic Reference Corpus of Medieval French* (SRCMF) — significant gaps remain. In particular, there is a lack of high-quality training data enriched with detailed semantic annotation. While early experiments with training LLMs on Old French have produced encouraging results, they have been limited in both scale and depth.

2 Related Work

Studies on NLP for Medieval French, such as Grobol et al., 2021 and Guibon et al., 2014, have highlighted the difficulty of parsing Medieval French. Results from other studies, such as Kezarian et al., 2024, also suggest that distinguishing between Medieval and Modern French is complicated.

The primary resource for experiments with Medieval French text has been the *Syntactic Reference Corpus of Medieval French* (SRCMF) by Stein and Prévost, 2013. Originally a treebank, the SRCMF has been adapted to conform to the Universal Dependencies (UD) standards. The SRCMF dataset, however, is not comprehensive as it is primarily restricted to Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging and does not include annotations for lemmata. Studies such as Stein, 2014 to compare dependency parsers and Grobol et al., 2022 to evaluate the usage of contextual word embedding models for downstream tasks such as POS tagging and dependency parsing have used the dataset as training data and achieved promising results, despite the limited features of the dataset.

For the *Pyrrha*² ecosystem by Camps et al., 2021, a tagger for Old French, the *OFr3C* corpus was assembled from juridical texts from the *Corpus juris civilis* (École Nationale des Chartes), a codification of Roman law, translated into French, and literary text genres such as the *Chansons de Geste* and the *Roman Courtois*; for the latter, the preexisting *Chrétien* corpus, compiled for the *Dictionnaire Électronique de Chrétien de Troyes* (Kunstmann and Souvay, 2016), was reused.

The part-of-speech annotations are complex, accounting for the various pronoun categories (per-

²<https://dh.chartes.psl.eu/pyrrha/>

sonal, demonstrative, indefinite, interrogative, relative, adverbial, impersonal, cardinal, ordinal), and times, and mode and person are also specified for verbs; for a reference lexeme inventory, *Pyrrha* uses the *Altfranzösisches Wörterbuch* by Tobler and Lommatzsch - TL (Tobler and Lommatzsch, 1915–1976; 1989-1995; 2002). They also included annotations for contractions, agglutinations and non-bounded terms, named entities and homonyms, among other details.

3 ALMeD

While existing corpora such as the *OFr3C* corpus and the *Base de Français Médiéval* - BFM, ENS de Lyon, Laboratoire IHRIM (Guillot et al., 2018), are available, they are relatively small and mainly focus on literary texts. In contrast, ALMeD is domain-specific. While its technical texts, of course, also contain non-technical language at large, they account for specialised terminology seldom covered by the *belles lettres*.³ ALMeD focuses on medieval medical texts that contain highly complex medical and surgical terminology, which makes it suitable not only for NLP-related tasks of the *Knowledge Networks in Medieval Romance Speaking Europe* (ALMA) project.⁴ project, but it also holds potential for research on technical texts more broadly. Although medical and surgical terminology is highly specialised, these texts share with other technical domains the communicative practices typical of technical language — practices that were shaped historically and transmitted as part of a broader tradition of discourse. ALMeD focuses on medieval medical texts containing highly complex medical and anatomical terminology. While it is primarily designed to support NLP-related tasks within the ALMA project, it may also be of interest for research on technical texts more broadly. Although medical and surgical terminology is highly specialised, these texts share with other technical domains a range of communicative practices typical of technical language, such as standardised modes of description, instruction, and argumentation. These practices were historically established

³With notable exceptions, e.g., we find sophisticated ship-building terminology in a hagiographical Anglo-Norman text from ca 1193 (Kjellman, 1935), technical terms of several domains in the *Roman de la Rose* from ca 1230/ca 1275 (Dörr, 2016), etc.

⁴Based at the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities, and the Academy of Sciences and Literature Mainz, <https://www.hadw-bw.de/alma> [2026-01-29].

and transmitted over time, reflecting a broader tradition of technical discourse. The gold-standard fine-grained annotated dataset will consist of texts from the medical corpus of the ALMA project. Using the *Dictionnaire étymologique de l'ancien français* (DEAF, Baldinger, 1971-2020) as the primary lexicographic reference, these texts have been semantically disambiguated and annotated for several key linguistic features: part-of-speech, including the universal part-of-speech (UPOS) and the language-specific part-of-speech (XPOS), lemma, main lemma (standard headword form of the word), named entities, glossary definitions (of medical and surgical terms provided in the critical text editions), and dictionary definitions in modern French and English (see below).

Texts Used

At the time of writing, the following texts are being annotated and validated:

1. The *Chappitre singulier* (an overview over the history of medicine and the medical society at the time) and the second treatise (on tumors, cancer, and the plague) of the *Grande Chirurgie* by Gui de Chauliac, Middle French, (text after 1363) manuscript 2nd third 15th c., edition in preparation by ALMA; around 12,000 tokens - annotation in progress.
2. The first treatise (on anatomy) of the same text, edition by Sabine Tittel (Tittel, 2004); around 32,000 tokens - annotation completed, currently being corrected.
3. *The Surgery of Albucasis*, edition by David Trotter (Trotter, 2005), Lorraine scripta, mid 13th c.; around 130,000 tokens - annotation completed, currently being corrected.
4. *Lettre d'Hippocrate à César*, edition by Tony Hunt (Hunt, 1990), Anglo-Norman scripta, 2nd quarter 13th c.; around 24,000 tokens - completed.

Part of Speech Tagging

For the part-of-speech (POS) tagging, two tagsets will be used. The first is Universal Part-of-Speech (UPOS) tags as per the Universal Dependencies (UD), which is a framework for consistent annotation of grammar across different languages. Using the UD format is particularly useful in standardising annotations for a project like ALMA that works

with four languages. The second set of POS tags used are the language-specific tags (XPOS), which are even more fine-grained than the UPOS.

We chose the Universal Dependencies for two reasons:

1. Since it is the accepted standard framework for linguistic annotation, we aimed to maximise the reusability of our data, particularly for downstream learning tasks, such as low-resource settings and multilingual training.
2. In ALMA, we work with multiple languages, including Old Occitan and Old Italian. We also align parallel texts in two languages; for example, ChirAlbT has textual transmissions in Old French and Old Occitan, while GuiChaul has transmissions in Old Italian and Middle French. While XPOS is language-specific and fine-grained, we treat UPOS as a point of commonality. This is particularly relevant for our lexical-semantic studies, as it allows us to examine how a given word is tagged across languages: does it belong to a different part of speech in each language, and if so, why? Do other factors, such as historical context, account for these differences?

For the language-specific morpho-syntactic (XPOS) tags, we use the CATTEX tagset (Guillot et al., 2018). The CATTEX tags comprise two fields: category and type. The categories mostly correspond to the classic parts of speech: VER (verb), NOM (noun), ADJ (adjective), PRO (pronoun), DET (determiner), ADV (adverb), PRE (preposition), CON (conjunction), INJ (interjection). Each linguistic unit has a single morphological label, composed of the category and type (except for the categories PRE, ETR, ABR, RED and OUT, which include only the category name). Labelling is morphosyntactic in the sense that categories and types are determined in context according to primarily morphological principles (strictly syntactic annotation is also carried out). We also account for named entities with two additional custom tags PROPNper (Proper Noun Person) and PROPNpla (Proper Noun Place).

Lemmatisation

One of the key issues in NLP for Medieval French is lemmatisation, i.e., assigning variant graphical realisations of a lexeme to a form defined as a standard, called a lemma. The lemmatisation is

a crucial step because of the lack of spelling normalisation in that period: A given lemma can be expressed in many different spellings and, on the other hand, a given spelling can be an expression of different lemmata (for challenges and implications, cf. Tittel, 2024, 192-199). The lemmatisation thus also determines the POS of the lexeme (and it also maps inflected verb occurrences to the appropriate lemma).

While there has been some success in developing a fairly accurate lemmatiser for medieval French, Pyrrha (which is based on the TL lemmata), the training data used by the developers is primarily focused on literary and juridical texts. This means that scientific texts and terminology have not been accounted for. To annotate the lemma, we use the lemma list of the DEAF as our primary reference, which contains around 84,000 lemmata. This makes it the most comprehensive dictionary of Old French. The lemmatisation of the DEAF corresponds to a 12th-century French accepted as 'standard form' in the discipline; it therewith adopts the rules of the TL, but corrects them in line with modern practice, e.g. with regard to umlaut placement. However, in cases where the word is not listed in the DEAF, other dictionaries are referenced, such as the *Anglo-Norman Dictionary* (AND)⁵ and the *Dictionnaire du Moyen Français* (DMF)⁶.

Since the DEAF is a dictionary that groups its entries by word families to make etymological relations visible, there is also the added benefit of including the main lemma — the lemma of the word family — in our lemmatisation process.

Glossary Definitions

As this dataset focuses on medical terminology, we include glossary definitions of medical and anatomical terms drawn from the critical editions of the medieval manuscripts. The glossary is essential for sense definitions and, thus, for semantic disambiguation in context. For instance, in the GuiChaulMT edition (Tittel, 2004, 299), there is a glossary entry, *chief* (masculine), recorded with two senses depending on context:

- 1° "upper part of the human body, head", attested in lines 319; 333; 339; 346; 350; 356; 358; 359; 360; 370; etc.
- 2° "terminal part of something (of a bone, etc.); tip", attested in lines 201; 219; 320

⁵<https://anglo-norman.net/>

⁶<http://zeus.atilf.fr/dmf/>

The correct contextual usage of this word in both definitions is indicated in the Glossary by the references to the lines in which the word occurs, which makes it a vital resource for semantic disambiguation. There are many such instances in which such general and domain-specific terms have several meanings; therefore, these instances will be tagged with the appropriate definition. Since there is currently no all-encompassing resource with a complete lexeme inventory and state-of-the-art genus-differentia definitions of all senses that could serve as a centralised dataset, this approach helps fill in lexicographic gaps. This is particularly important in all cases where the corresponding dictionary entry in the DEAF is part of DEAF*pré*.⁷

Dictionary Definitions

We also include the dictionary definitions of key words and terms from the various Old French to Modern French and Old French to Modern English dictionaries, to resolve semantic ambiguity as much as possible.

Medieval French to Modern French

For the Modern French sense definitions, we rely on five dictionaries: DEAF, AND, DMF, *Tobler-Lommatzsch* (TL), and the *Französisches Etymologisches Wörterbuch* (FEW). Among these, the DEAF serves as the primary lexicographic reference and provides the majority of our definitions. This preference reflects both ALMA's conceptual continuity with the DEAF project and our privileged access to key resources such as its lemma list. AND, DMF and the other dictionaries are used in cases where the word is not listed in the DEAF.

Medieval French to Modern English

For the English sense definitions, we use two dictionaries: *Anglo-Norman Dictionary*⁸ and the *Old French-English Dictionary* by Hindley et al., 2006 for standard definitions. While neither dictionary is comprehensive nor do they contain detailed lexicographic and etymological information, these are the best medieval French-to-English resources available, and can be used for basic tasks.

Annotation Process

To annotate the texts, we use the semantic annotation platform INCEPTION (Klie et al., 2018).

⁷For the differences of DEAF*pré* and DEAF*plus*, see Tittel, 2023, 48.

⁸<https://anglo-norman.net/>

Figure 1: Annotating *Lettre d'Hippocrate*, an Anglo-Norman text on INCEpTION

While we initially considered other tools, such as TXM and CATMA, INCEpTION proved to be the most suitable for our objectives. Its capabilities—specifically designed for the creation of training data—include preset layers for Universal Dependencies, support for custom annotation layers (e.g. glossary and dictionary definitions), recommender systems that accelerate the annotation process, broad file-format compatibility (in particular XML/TEI), and built-in automatic tokenisation and sentence segmentation.

We have four standard layers for every token: part-of-speech (UPOS and XPOS), lemma and main lemma — a minimum of four labels per token. The glossary and dictionary definitions are tagged once; however, in situations where one word has two meanings, the token is assigned its contextually accurate definition (see Figure 1). INCEpTION’s layer functionalities also allow us to differentiate between the dictionary sources used, thereby making it easier to trace the definitions back to their origin, ensure consistency across annotations, and resolve cases where multiple resources provide overlapping or conflicting information.

4 Future Work

We aim to create a complete gold standard comprising upwards of 50,000 tokens annotated and texts semantically disambiguated, and present ALMeD as a suitable, domain-specific alternative to the SR-CMF dataset. In contrast to existing resources, ALMeD will capture not only morphosyntactic information but also semantic and domain-specific

layers, making it a richer dataset for the study of medieval medical French texts.

ALMeD will also be used internally by the ALMA project for, among other things, our NLP research, supporting the development and evaluation of new tools, models, and methodologies. ALMeD is also the foundation for a dedicated language model for Medieval French that we are currently developing, HeidelBERT.

The first version of ALMeD is publicly available on Hugging Face. As the annotation is still ongoing, we will progressively make more data available to the research community as a reusable and extensible resource for more accurate linguistic analysis, improved language models, and a solid foundation for future research, not only in medieval French linguistics but also in NLP for under-resourced languages.

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Down the Slavic Memory Lane: A Unified Old Church Slavonic Corpus for Core NLP Tasks

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Abstract

This work introduces a large, unified Old Church Slavonic (OCS) corpus to address the under-representation of OCS texts in a standardized digital format. The openly licensed corpus merges 45 heterogeneous sources into a single dataset containing 256,000 text segments, which amounts to 4.4 million tokens. All texts feature standardized Unicode encoding and retain their full diacritics. To demonstrate the corpus’s usability for core NLP tasks, a six-class genre classifier was developed by fine-tuning a RuBERT model, achieving a weighted F1 score of 0.8. The complete corpus, preprocessing script, and the fine-tuned model are publicly available at <https://huggingface.co/datasets/z00logist/OldChurchSlavonic> and <https://huggingface.co/z00logist/rubert-ocs-classifier>.

1 Introduction

Large multilingual corpora drive much of modern NLP, but low-resource and extinct languages still lack comparable datasets. OCS, preserved mainly in ninth- to eleventh-century ecclesiastical manuscripts (Dvornik, 1956; Huntley, 1993), is a prime example despite its strong influence on later Slavic languages.

Existing OCS resources, such as parts of the PROIEL Corpus (Eckhoff et al., 2018) and the Tromsø Old Russian and Old Church Slavonic Treebank (Berdicevskis and Eckhoff, 2020), are fragmented, use varying encodings, and follow inconsistent annotation schemes. These issues complicate text normalization, hinder language-model training, and limit detailed morphological analysis.

The present work addresses these limitations by consolidating 45 sources into a single CC-BY corpus with uniform encoding and retained diacritics. A genre-classification benchmark offers

an initial performance baseline and illustrates the dataset’s consistency. Moreover, the present corpus of 4.4 million tokens represents a more than 20-fold increase in the amount of openly accessible, standardized OCS data compared to existing linguistic treebanks like the Universal Dependencies (UD) OCS corpus.

The corpus targets two main audiences: (i) *computational and historical linguists*, who can use it for quantitative studies of orthographic and diacritic variation, stylometry, and cross-manuscript/recension comparison while retaining provenance via the Source field; and (ii) *NLP researchers and practitioners working on low-resource or historical-language NLP*, who can use it for continued pretraining of Cyrillic language models, supervised document/segment classification (e.g., genre, source, recension), and evaluation of transfer from modern Slavic languages. Sentence-level segmentation supports standard pipelines for token and sequence classification as well as retrieval/duplication studies, while preserved diacritics provide fine-grained morphological cues. CC-BY licensing and unified Unicode encoding lower the barrier to reproducible experimentation and classroom use.

2 Related Work

OCS texts remain under-represented; several historical Slavic corpora have appeared in recent years. The “Panchrony” sub-corpus of the Russian National Corpus (Sitchinava, 2024), the “Old Russian” sub-corpus (Dobrushina et al., 2015), and the “Manuscript” corpus from Izhevsk (https://mns.udsu.ru/?p_lid=1) all support diachronic and paleographic research. Each, however, offers only partial OCS coverage and applies annotations inconsistently, which hampers cross-corpus comparison.

Recent initiatives address this fragmentation.

Metric	Value
Number of rows	256,890
Total file size (MB)	23.5
Number of sentences	295,680
Total tokens	4,386,976
Unique tokens	239,835
Average tokens per sentence	14.84

Table 1: Dataset Statistics.

4 Dataset Statistics

The dataset contains 256,890 rows and measures approximately 23.5 MB in raw and Parquet formats on HuggingFace. It includes 4,386,976 tokens distributed over 295,680 sentences, yielding an average of 14.84 tokens per sentence. There are 239,835 unique tokens, including all unique word-forms as the dataset was not lemmatized for counting statistics. These statistics are summarized in the following table: The dataset is structured with one text segment per row. While most rows correspond to a single sentence, some source texts contained line breaks within sentences or multiple short sentences on a single line. Therefore, the number of rows (256,890) is the primary unit of the dataset, from which we heuristically identified a slightly larger number of sentences (295,680) for statistical purposes.

These statistics suggest that further preprocessing or normalization steps may be necessary for specific tasks. For example, the presence of orthographic variants and diacritic inconsistencies between sources might require targeted normalization to improve the accuracy of downstream tasks, such as lemmatization or part-of-speech tagging. In contrast, preserving such variations could benefit comparative studies in historical linguistics, particularly those examining regional or temporal shifts in language usage.

5 Genre Classification Experiment

A genre- or source- classification task was selected to demonstrate one concrete downstream use of the corpus. The objective is illustrative rather than competitive: the experiment establishes a reasonable baseline and confirms that modern transformer models can cope with the orthographic and stylistic variability of OCS texts.

The original dataset contains 45 manuscript-level source labels (e.g., *apostol*, *marianus*). To mitigate sparsity and improve interpretability,

Class	Count
<i>liturgical_books</i>	68,642
<i>minea</i>	65,944
<i>hagiography</i>	51,220
<i>scriptures</i>	44,257
<i>instructional_texts</i>	14,868
<i>hymnals</i>	11,959

Table 2: Distribution of samples across six merged classes.

a rule-based mapping merged these labels into six broader categories: *liturgical books*, *minea* (monthly service books), *hagiography*, *scriptures*, *instructional texts*, and *hymnals*. Table 2 reports the resulting class distribution.

RuBERT, a Russian-language BERT variant (Kuratov and Arkhipov, 2019), was chosen as the model to fine-tune. Its Cyrillic vocabulary reduces the script-mismatch overhead typical of multilingual checkpoints while still providing robust subword coverage for Old Church Slavonic. While multilingual models like XLM-RoBERTa (Conneau et al., 2020) present a strong alternative, RuBERT was chosen to explicitly test transfer learning from a modern, though divergent, linguistic relative within the same script. This approach isolates the challenges of diachronic linguistic drift (from OCS to modern Russian) within a shared Cyrillic script, providing a focused baseline on language family transfer. The corpus was stratified by genre into 80%/10%/10% splits. Implementation followed standard practice: a BertTokenizerFast with a 128-token window, the AdamW optimiser (Loshchilov and Hutter, 2019), ten epochs, and weighted cross-entropy to counter class imbalance. Full hyper-parameter details and training logs are provided in Appendix A

1. Applying a built-in BERT-compatible tokenizer BertTokenizerFast with a maximum sequence length of 128 tokens.
2. Casting labels to a fixed index set (0-5) corresponding to the six classes.

Model performance metrics on the test set are presented in Table 3.

Weighted F_1 (0.8) and ROC-AUC (0.96) indicate substantial separability among the six genres (Table 3). A confusion-matrix inspection (complete version in Appendix B) confirms that

Metric	Value
Accuracy	0.8058
F1 (weighted)	0.8047
F1 (macro)	0.7641
ROC-AUC (weighted)	0.9587

Table 3: Text classification performance on the six-category OCS dataset.

the primary source of error is the confusion between liturgical books and scriptures. This overlap is predictable, as liturgical services are fundamentally structured around scriptural readings, psalms, and direct quotations, making short textual segments lexically and stylistically indistinguishable. A similar, albeit lesser, confusion occurs between hymnals and minea, since the minea are themselves composed largely of hymns dedicated to specific feasts and saints. The remaining misclassifications typically involve short, context-poor segments or orthographic variants not encountered during pre-training.

The experiment confirms that the corpus is sufficient to transformer-based methods without extensive hand-crafted normalization. Beyond genre classification, the same data can inform stylometric studies, diachronic morphology, or alignment in machine translation pipelines. The baseline therefore serves as a reference point rather than an end goal; future work may explore domain-specific pre-training, character-level models, or hierarchical architectures better suited to liturgical discourse.

6 Limitations

The corpus remains skewed toward liturgical and hagiographic material, so models trained on it may generalize poorly to secular or administrative registers. Orthographic and diacritic variation has been preserved to aid in philological work, yet this heterogeneity complicates downstream tasks such as lemmatization and part-of-speech tagging. Baseline experiments rely on RuBERT, a model pretrained in modern Russian; although script overlap offers a practical starting point, linguistic divergence can introduce representational bias. The text has undergone only spot-checking, leaving occasional OCR noise or truncated lines, and chronological as well as regional coverage is uneven, with South-Slavonic and late Russian OCS recensions still underrepresented.

Furthermore, the classification baseline, while illustrative, does not fully exploit the rich diacritical data preserved in the corpus. Future work should explore tasks like morphological tagging or recension identification that are more sensitive to these features. A comparative analysis against multilingual models like XLM-R would also provide a more robust performance benchmark.

7 Ethical and Legal Considerations

All texts included in the corpus were drawn from repositories that either publish material in the public domain or grant explicit permission for scholarly redistribution. The *Corpus Cyrillo-Methodianum Helsingiense*, now hosted in the Finnish Language Bank, offers a publicly accessible version of its OCS holdings under an open license intended for unrestricted academic use. Orthlib provides facsimiles of pre-modern liturgical books whose authors are long deceased; the website explicitly allows re-use and re-publishing the materials. The St Petersburg “SCAT” corpus of hagiographic texts is made available for open academic research; and the project team encourages citation of its XML releases. Throughout the compilation process, each source was cited in the metadata to ensure that credit remains traceable to the original compilers and digitizers. No personal data appear in any text, and the consolidated corpus is released under CC-BY 4.0, allowing free redistribution provided that original sources are acknowledged.

8 Conclusion

This study introduces a 256k-segment Old Church Slavonic corpus, normalized and released under a permissive license to encourage reproducible research. Forty-five manuscript labels were mapped into six genre classes, enabling a baseline RuBERT classifier to achieve 81 % accuracy and a weighted F_1 of 0.8. Error analysis highlights predictable overlap between liturgical and scriptural texts and underscores the impact of orthographic variation.

Planned extensions include (i) a parallel Russian–OCS corpus to support machine translation and cross-lingual transfer, (ii) synthetic augmentation through controlled paraphrasing and language-model generation, and (iii) an open-source preprocessing toolkit covering

tokenization, lemmatization, and part-of-speech tagging specifically tailored to OCS morphology.

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A Training Configuration

A.1 Hyperparameters

Parameter	Value
Base checkpoint	DeepPavlov/rubert-base-cased
Tokenizer	BertTokenizerFast
Maximum sequence length	128 tokens
Optimiser	AdamW
Learning rate	5×10^{-5}
Batch size (train / eval)	8 / 8
Epochs	10
Mixed precision	FP16
Loss function	Cross-entropy + class weights
Class-weight cap	5.0
Evaluation strategy	Per epoch
Metric for best model	Weighted F ₁
Checkpoint limit	2

Table 4: Hyper-parameter settings for the RuBERT genre-classification baseline.

A.2 Data Splits

- **Train** – 205 512 segments (80 %)
- **Validation** – 25 689 segments (10 %)
- **Test** – 25 689 segments (10 %)

Splits were produced with stratified sampling (`random_state = 42`) to preserve class ratios.

B Confusion Matrix

Table 5 shows the confusion matrix of the RuBERT-based genre classification experiment. Categories are abbreviated as follows: (A) liturgical books, (B) minea, (C) hagiography, (D) scriptures, (E) instructional texts, and (F) hymnals.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
A	4730	25	44	103	30	190
B	54	579	34	251	191	87
C	30	35	1100	150	67	105
D	141	138	128	5425	862	170
E	37	146	55	960	5221	176
F	211	99	105	217	149	3644

Table 5: Confusion matrix of genre classification (A: liturgical books, B: minea, C: hagiography, D: scriptures, E: instructional texts, F: hymnals). Rows correspond to **true** labels; columns correspond to **predicted** labels.

Context Matters: Probing the Robustness of Sentence Embeddings for Intertextuality Detection in Latin Texts

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Abstract

This paper investigates sentence embeddings as a tool for detecting intertextual references and paraphrased reuse in Latin texts. We fine-tune a Sentence Transformer (SPhilBERTa) on a curated dataset of 545 intertextual pairs from Jerome and Lactantius, paired with candidate sentences from Virgil and other classical authors. To better understand model behavior, we conduct a controlled modification study on a small qualitative sample in which query sentences are systematically altered through reductions of word material (citation-only, content words only, function words only), morphological changes (case, number, tense, mood), and semantic-syntactic changes (two degrees of paraphrase and limited reordering), and we track the resulting shifts in cosine similarity. We find that long verbatim quotations yield stable embedding similarities under inflectional variation and mild paraphrase; stronger paraphrase leads to moderate decreases, while reordering has only minor effects. By contrast, very short allusions and intertextual links embedded in strongly diverging semantic contexts remain challenging.

1 Introduction

For centuries, scholars of classical texts relied on memory and intuition to identify citations within writings (Conte, 1986; Hinds, 1998; Wills, 1996; Barchiesi, 2001; Edmunds, 2001). In recent decades, tools such as the *Library of Latin Texts* (LLT) have simplified this task by enabling large-scale lexical research. In the age of AI, language models offer new possibilities to capture semantic and contextual similarity beyond exact word matches (Devlin et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2019).

This paper examines the potential of sentence embedding models for detecting intertextual references in Latin texts. While embeddings have been applied successfully to related tasks (Bamman and Burns, 2020; Burns et al., 2021; Gong et al., 2025),

their robustness in capturing the particular linguistic variability of Latin texts remains underexplored.

As an experimental setting, this analysis evaluates the behavior of sentence embeddings under controlled textual modifications. For a stratified sampled dataset of confirmed intertextual links (source-query pairs), we apply three classes of systematic linguistic changes to the query sentence: (a) reductions to specific word material (citation-only, content words only, function words only), (b) morphological modifications (in case, number, tense, mood), and (c) semantic-syntactic modifications (two degrees of paraphrase and limited reordering). We then track the resulting shifts in cosine similarity. In addition, we contrast each case with a non-intertextual, randomly sampled sentence within the same source author’s corpus to contextualize the magnitude of the observed changes. This design allows us to probe which textual cues the model treats as similarity-preserving or similarity-disrupting, thereby offering insight into the implicit criteria that drive its ranking decisions. Given the small, curated sample ($N = 11$) we treat our study as a controlled probe of the model’s sensitivity to different forms of textual variation rather than a benchmark evaluation, which is crucial given that Latin intertextuality often manifests not as verbatim quotation but as paraphrase, reformulation, or subtle allusion.

2 Related Work

Recent work has advanced NLP for Latin, from morphological analysis tools to shared-task evaluation and transformer-based tagging and lemmatization (Passarotti et al., 2017; Sprugnoli et al., 2020; Wróbel and Nowak, 2022), within a broader ecosystem of digital approaches to ancient languages (Sommerschild et al., 2023).

Previous research on Latin intertextuality has focused on lexical and metric-verbal co-occurrences (Coffee et al., 2012; Kozák, 2018; Venuti et al.,

2023; Schropp et al., 2024a) or prioritized matching word-level embeddings: Burns et al. (2021) employed static Word2Vec models trained on lemmatized text to rank intertextual bigrams. Validated on a curated dataset of 945 parallels from Valerius Flaccus’ *Argonautica*, their approach outperformed traditional lexical methods in capturing semantic and syntactic similarities, yielding significant results in synonym and anomaly detection.

Addressing the inability of static embeddings to handle context-dependent polysemy, Gong et al. (2025) substituted Word2vec with LatinBERT (Bamman and Burns, 2020) to generate context-specific token embeddings, which are used to retrieve similar source phrases and identify allusions in Lucan’s *Pharsalia*.

Both Burns et al. (2021) and Gong et al. (2025) extract embeddings for individual word units rather than entire phrases. In contrast, Riemenschneider and Frank (2023) applied the Sentence Transformer architecture (Reimers and Gurevych, 2019) to ancient languages. They introduced SPhilBERTa, a multilingual model fine-tuned on parallel sentences in Ancient Greek, Latin, and English. By combining sentence-pair matching with binary classification, they achieved over 95% accuracy on cross-lingual retrieval benchmarks, demonstrating the efficacy of encoding full text passages.

Krahn et al. (2023) train and evaluate sentence embedding models tailored to Ancient Greek, using multilingual knowledge distillation to obtain semantically meaningful sentence representations; Craig et al. (2023) assess neural sentence-alignment for Classical Greek and Latin texts and translations, testing multilingual sentence-embedding models as alignment signals.

Recent work evaluates automatic intertextuality detection with curated benchmarks and quantitative metrics, paired with inter-annotator agreement to assess the reliability of “gold” links (Manjavacas et al., 2019; Dexter et al., 2024; Schelb et al., 2026).

Most recent research primarily relies on benchmarks and quantitative metrics for evaluation, but rarely offers hypotheses on when models work well and when they do not. To address this gap, our study adopts a qualitative, diagnostic probing approach that tests how controlled morphological, lexical, and structural modifications affect similarity scores.

3 Methods

3.1 Retrieval Pipeline

We approach the task of identifying intertextual links as an information retrieval problem (Manning et al., 2009). Moving beyond traditional lexical overlap methods (Manjavacas et al., 2019), we employ the Sentence Transformer architecture (Reimers and Gurevych, 2019) to generate one dense vector representations per text segment in the *query* (e.g., Jerome) and *source* corpora (e.g., classical authors). The model is fine-tuned to minimize the distance between intertextually linked pairs while maximizing the distance between unrelated segments. During inference, the system computes pairwise cosine similarities between every query and source segment (i.e. sentence). By ranking the candidates by their proximity in vector space we identify candidates for the most probable intertextual references (Schelb et al., 2026).

3.2 Perturbation Study

To complement aggregate retrieval performance with a more diagnostic analysis, we adopt a controlled modification paradigm inspired by behavioral testing in NLP (Ribeiro et al., 2020) and by contrast-set evaluation, which probes model behavior through small, targeted edits to otherwise fixed instances (Gardner et al., 2020). Concretely, we start from a set of confirmed intertextual sentence pairs and generate structured variants of the query sentence while keeping the corresponding source sentence fixed. This yields minimal-pair style comparisons that allow us to attribute changes in cosine similarity to specific factors rather than to uncontrolled differences in content.

The modifications are designed to probe (a) the role of contextual framing versus citation content density (reductions to citation-only material, content words only, and function words only), (b) sensitivity to morphological variation typical of Latin reuse (case, number, tense, mood, and a combination thereof), and (c) robustness to semantic-syntactic reformulation (graded paraphrase and limited local reordering).¹ As an additional reference point for similarity values, each case is contrasted with a randomly sampled, non-intertextual sentence

¹While reductions (a) are performed on the whole sentence, the modifications in (b) and (c) are limited to the citation material so that any change in cosine similarity can be attributed to variation in the intertextual signal itself rather than to shifts in the surrounding context.

from the source author’s corpus. In contrast to counterfactually augmented data, which uses minimal edits to construct training and evaluation sets (Kaushik et al., 2020), our goal here is not data augmentation but interpretability: to characterize which controlled changes the embedding model treats as similarity-preserving and which changes disrupt the intertextual signal.

4 Experimental Setup

4.1 Dataset for Retrieval Pipeline

Compiling extensive data on intertextual references among ancient texts often involves substantial emendatory work, since the relevant material is dispersed across commentaries, *indices locorum*, and case specific scholarship. The dataset of 545 confirmed intertextual references used in this study consists of manually reviewed citations in Jerome’s epistles from Virgil and Cicero (Schropp et al., 2024b). Additional cases stem from an N-gram matching process on a rule-based Python script basis comparing two Latin texts sentence by sentence to identify identical words (Schropp et al., 2024a; Wittweiler et al., 2025). Candidate matches for Jerome and Lactantius against a selection of classical poets were manually evaluated, retaining only meaningful intertextual sentence pairs (Schelb et al., 2026). These two sources were then combined into the training dataset shown in Figure 1.

4.2 Model Training and Evaluation

For our retrieval experiments, we treat sentence pairs manually identified as intertextual links as positive training examples (query, matching phrase, True). For every positive related sentence pair, we add 10 unrelated negative pairs sampled from our dataset by matching the query sentences from Jerome with a random sentence from the corpus (query, non-matching phrase, False).

To ensure the robustness of our findings, we use k-folds cross-validation with 5 folds, where the query sentences in each fold are excluded from the training set once and act as the test queries for evaluation.

We use the SPhilBERTa Model by Riemschneider and Frank (2023) as a base and fine-tune it for 4 epochs using Online Contrastive Loss with a learning rate of 2e-05 and batch size of 32. For evaluation, we use the trained model to compute embeddings for each phrase in the corpus and the query sentences in the test dataset, ranking the can-

didates from the corpus by cosine similarity. Finally, we calculate standard information retrieval metrics to assess the success of the model training.

4.3 Dataset for Perturbation study

We compiled a small test set of N=11 sentence pairs representing intertextual references attested in the scholarly literature (Table 1). We used a stratified selection scheme to ensure coverage of the intertextual phenomena in our material by covering four overlap-length citation types: (i) two-word congruencies, (ii) three-word congruencies, (iii) one-verse citations (approx. 5–8 words in prose), and (iv) two-verse citations (approx. 11–15 words in prose). These strata are represented across three author pairings (Jerome–Virgil, Jerome–Cicero, and Lactantius–Virgil/Lucretius) with one material-driven exception: in the Lactantius pairings, no two-word congruencies attested in the literature met our inclusion criteria.²

4.4 Model-Based Predictions

From the model properties outlined in subsection 3.1, we derive the following testable predictions:

- **Reduction effects:** Reductions to citation-only material and to content words should, if anything, lead to only small drops in cosine similarity, whereas reductions to function words should decrease similarity more substantially.
- **Morphological robustness:** Changes in inflectional morphology (case, number, tense, mood) should have only a limited effect on cosine similarity.
- **Semantic-syntactic robustness:** Moderate paraphrasing and limited word reordering should reduce cosine similarity only slightly.

To run the perturbation variants consistently and compute their respective similarity values, we implement a small web tool that takes a corpus file and a list of sentence pairs as input and returns the corresponding cosine similarities under a fixed retrieval pipeline.³

²The dataset used in this study is available on Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18435591>

³The code for this tool is publicly available: <https://github.com/julianschelb/latin-intertextuality-inspector>.

Figure 1: Intertextual links between authors in the annotated dataset. Line colors denote the citing author.

5 Qualitative Interpretation of Probing Results

5.1 Effect of Citation Content Density

Even under the controlled perturbations, similarity scores generally remain well above those obtained when pairing the query with the randomly sampled sentence (see table 2 in the Appendix); in median, the random baseline lies 0.34 points below the unmodified original.⁴

Across our dataset, reductions behave differently depending on the length and nature of the intertextual signal. Reducing a sentence to content words only largely preserves similarity and often yields values close to the unmodified query (-0.01 in median), suggesting that embeddings are driven primarily by semantically informative tokens rather than by grammatical scaffolding. By contrast, restricting the sentence to function words only produces the largest similarity drop (-0.17), suggesting that function-word overlap is not a reliable cue for intertextuality in the model and can easily be dominated by generic syntactic similarity. At the same time, even this reduced similarity often remains higher than that of the randomly sampled comparison (-0.34). This indicates that the model still derives some signal from function words, even though it is markedly weaker than the signal contributed by content words.

⁴In case 7, however, the random baseline scores 0.13 points higher than the actual source sentence. Although the citation spans five words, this result is best explained by the strongly diverging lexical fields of the surrounding context (assassination of Caesar vs. Christianity, marriage, and chastity), which yields a relatively low similarity score for the intertextual link in the first place.

Most importantly, reducing the query to citation-only material is not uniformly beneficial (ranging from +0.1 to -0.1). For long, literal quotations the citation material itself is sufficiently distinctive to dominate the pooled representation, and condensation often strengthens the signal by removing potentially diluting context. In our setup, long quotations are additionally advantaged by the use of the sentence as the retrieval unit: in some instances, an entire sentence consists almost exclusively of the quoted material. This is illustrated by case 4, where the source sentence is identical to the reduction to cited words only, yielding a cosine similarity of 1 (+0.1). For shorter allusions, however, the quotation material may be too small to anchor the sentence embedding on its own; in such cases, context can actively support retrieval by providing semantically aligned cues.

This pattern becomes clear in close readings of individual examples. Consider the citation in case 3: *Et nati natorum, et qui nascentur ab illis* (even his children’s children and their race that shall be born of them). In Jerome, the quoted Virgilian words are embedded in a dense network of contextual family vocabulary *gentem* (kin), *patres* (fathers), *fili* (sons), *nepotes* (grandchildren), alongside an explicit cue to Virgil *iuxta illud Virgilianum* (according to Vergil). In addition, the passage strongly emphasizes the permanence of residence *habitaturi autem non in alia terra, sed in ea ...* (but they will not live in a foreign land but in this ...), which resonates with Virgil’s dynastic register *hic domus Aeneae cunctis dominabitur oris* (there the house of Aeneas shall lord it over

all lands). Removing this contextual framing in Jerome strips away semantic bridges that otherwise strengthen the relationship between the two sentences, resulting in a decrease in cosine similarity of 0.06.

A reduction of 0.09 in cosine similarity can be observed in case 5 when condensing the Jerome passage to the shared material. Here, the shared expression *enaugavit oratio* (my discourse has sailed out) establishes the intertextual link to Cicero. In both texts, the nautical image is applied to the course of an argument, marking the transition from a difficult and obstructed section to a smoother continuation. Jerome, however, amplifies the metaphor with a dense cluster of related imagery: *e scopulosis locis* (from rocky places) and *et inter cauas spumeis fluctibus cautes fragilis in altum cumba processit* (and, amid the hollow rocks splashed by foaming waves, the fragile skiff has made its way out into the deep). Rather than introducing noise, this expanded context reinforces the same conceptual frame already present in Cicero and thus helps align the sentence embeddings. When the surrounding nautical vocabulary is removed, the cosine score drops accordingly.

These results show that condensation can help when the citation is long and lexically dominant, but it can weaken the signal for short allusions in which the intertextual signal is carried jointly by quotation and context.

5.2 Morphological Robustness

Across our cases, inflectional variation affects cosine similarity only marginally. Changes in case (median: -0.01) and number (-0.02) slightly reduce similarity to the unmodified queries, whereas changes in tense and mood have almost no measurable effect (+0.00). Even when multiple morphological changes are combined, the median shift remains small (-0.02). Overall, the model appears highly robust to Latin morphology, with embedding similarity shaped far more by lexical-semantic content than by inflectional form.

5.3 Paraphrase and Word Reordering

A more graded pattern emerges for semantic-syntactic modifications. Mild paraphrase through near-synonym substitutions is largely similarity-preserving and often yields values close to the original (median: +0.00). Stronger paraphrase results in a slightly larger decrease (-0.02), indicating that the model does react to semantically more divergent

lexical choices. Adding limited local reordering on top of stronger paraphrase tends to reduce similarity only slightly in median (-0.02); in a minority of cases, however, the score increases instead (4 out of 11), showing that reorderings are not consistently degrading similarity in this setting.

6 Conclusion

While interpreting the internal workings and decision-making processes of AI models remains a complex task, controlled perturbation probing can reveal which textual cues drive similarity in sentence embeddings and, by extension, what constitutes intertextual signal in our data.

Across the dataset, morphological variation, limited reordering and moderate paraphrase affect cosine similarity only slightly, indicating that the model is robust to many forms of textual transformation typical of text reuse. However, our findings are based on a small set of examples and should therefore be understood as diagnostic rather than representative of all intertextual phenomena. Moreover, by operating at the sentence level, our setup cannot fully capture cases where reuse spans sentence boundaries or where segmentation choices shape the available context. Future work should also follow up on mixed effects of limited word reordering observed in our perturbations.

Against this background, reductions to citation-only material reveal the central trade-off in sentence-embedding-based intertext detection: Where the citation is long and lexically distinctive, reducing the query to citation-only material can strengthen similarity by removing potentially diluting context. For short allusions, however, the surrounding context often provides the semantic bridge that makes the link detectable; in those cases, reduction can weaken the model's ability to recognize it. Our findings sharpen a central insight: context matters, not only for embedding robustness, but also for understanding intertextuality as a cultural and hermeneutic phenomenon.

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Appendix

Table 1: Original sentence pairs of the test set

All Latin texts used in this study were taken from freely available editions online, downloaded from [Corpus Corporum](#), the [Tesserae Project](#) and [Open Greek and Latin Project](#). Translations of Virgil, Lucretius and Cicero are taken from the [LOEB Classical Library](#). Translations of Jerome are by the authors. Translations of Lactantius are taken from [McDonald \(2008\)](#).

No.	Query ID	Source ID	Query	Source	Query Translation	Source Translation
1	hier. epist. 84.3.5	verg. aen. 11.282	credite experto , quasi Christianus Christianis loquor: uenenata sunt illius dogmata, aliena a scripturis sanctis, uim scripturis facientia.	Stetimus tela aspera contra contulimusque manus: experto credite , quantus in clipeum assurgat, quo turbine torqueat hastam.	Believe one who knows from experience , as though I were speaking as a Christian to Christians: his doctrines are poisonous, alien to the Holy Scriptures, because they do violence to them.	We have faced his fierce weapons, and fought him hand to hand: trust one who has experienced it , how huge he looms above his shield, with what whirlwind he hurls his spear!
2	hier. epist. 130.5.5	verg. aen. 3.47	haesit uox faucibus et inter ruborem atque pallorem metumque ac laetitiam cogitationes uariae mutabantur.	Tum vero ancipiti mentem formidine pressus obstipui, steteruntque comae et vox faucibus haesit .	The words stuck in their throats and amid blushing and paling, fear and joy, various thoughts kept shifting.	Then, indeed, with mind borne down with perplexing dread, I was appalled, my hair stood up, and the voice choked in my throat .

Continued on next page

No.	Query ID	Source ID	Query	Source	Query Translation	Source Translation
3	hier. in ezech. 0352c	verg. aen. 3.97	Qui postquam fuerint in gentem unam, et in terra Israel, ac montibus habitauerint, ambulaturi sint in omnibus iudiciis Domini, et praecepta illius custodituri; habitaturi autem non in alia terra, sed in ea quam dedit seruo suo Iacob, in qua habitauerunt patres eorum, Abraham, Isaac, et Iacob, et reliqui sancti, et non solum ipsi habitaturi sint, sed et filii eorum ac nepotes iuxta illud Uirgilianum: Et nati natorum, et qui nascentur ab illis: habitentque non ad breue tempus, sed in perpetuum.	hic domus Aeneae cunctis dominabitur oris et nati natorum et qui nascuntur ab illis.	After they have become one people and settled in the land of Israel and in the mountains, they will walk in all the commandments of the Lord and keep His statutes. They will not dwell in a foreign land, but in the one that Jacob gave to his servant, where their fathers dwelled: Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob, along with the other saints. Not only they themselves will live there, but also their sons and grandsons, in accordance with the saying of Virgil: even the children’s children and those who will be born of them. They shall not dwell there for a short time, but forever.	There the house of Aeneas shall lord it over all lands, even his children’s children and their race that shall be born of them.
4	hier. epist. 123.13.1	verg. aen. 4.548	cui breviter respondeat ipsa, quae passa est: tu lacrimis evicta meis, tu prima furentem his, germana, malis oneras atque obicis hosti.	tu lacrimis evicta meis, tu prima furentem his, germana, malis oneras atque obicis hosti.	Thereupon she, stricken by grief, gave a brief reply: You, sister, overcome by my tears, you were the first to burden me, frantic as I was, with these evils and to hand me over to the enemy.	Won over by my tears, you, my sister, you were the first to load my frenzied soul with these ills, and drive me on the foe.

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No.	Query ID	Source ID	Query	Source	Query Translation	Source Translation
5	hier. epist. 14.10.1	cic. tusc. 4.33	Sed quoniam e scopulosis locis enaugavit oratio et inter cauas spumeis fluctibus cautes fragilis in altum cumba processit, expandenda uela sunt uentis et quaestionum scopulis transuadatis laetantium more nautarum epilogi celeuma cantandum est.	ex quibus quoniam tamquam ex scrupulosis cotibus enavigavit oratio , reliquae disputationis cursum teneamus, modo satis illa dilucide dixerimus pro rerum obscuritate.	But now that my words have sailed out from the rocky shore, and this frail, little boat has steered out into the open sea between cliffs hollowed by foaming waves, the sails must be spread to the wind. After all the cliff-like questions have been sailed past, a shanty should be sung at the end, as is customary among cheerful sailors.	And now that our argument has worked its way , as it were, clear of these rocks with all their catchy points, let us pursue the course of the discussion that remains, provided only I have given an account which is adequately clear, considering the difficulty of the subject.
6	hier. epist. 108.3.4	cic. tusc. 1.109	fugiendo gloriam gloriam merebatur, quae virtutem umbra sequitur et appetitores sui deserens appetit contemptores.	etsi enim nihil habet in se gloria cur expetatur, tamen virtutem tamquam umbra sequitur .	In fleeing from fame, she won fame, which follows virtue like a shadow , leaving behind those who sought it and seeking out those who despised it.	There is, it may be, nothing in glory that we should desire it, but none the less it follows virtue like a shadow .

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No.	Query ID	Source ID	Query	Source	Query Translation	Source Translation
7	hier. epist. 54.6.3	cic. phil. 2.30	pater tuus, quem ego honoris causa nomino non quia consularis et patricius, sed quia Christianus est, inpleat nomen suum et laetetur filiam Christo se genuisse, non saeculo; quin potius doleat, quod et uirginitatem frustra amiseris et fructus perdideris nuptiarum.	Brutus, quem ego honoris causa nomino , cruentum pugionem tenens Ciceronem exclamavit: ex quo intellegi debet eum conscium fuisse.	Your father, whom I mention with respect , not because he is a patrician and a former consul, but because he is a Christian, may he prove worthy of his name and rejoice that he has given a daughter to Christ and not to the world; rather, he should grieve that you have lost your virginity in vain and have been unable to gain fruits of marriage.	Marcus Brutus, whose name I mention with respect , called on Cicero as he held his bloodstained dagger: hence it ought to be inferred that Cicero was in the plot.
8	hier. epist. 57.5.3	cic. opt. gen. 14	in quibus non pro uerbo uerbum necesse habui reddere, sed genus omnium uerborum uimque seruauit.	In quibus non uerbum pro uerbo necesse habui reddere, sed genus omne uerborum uimque seruavi.	in these I did not have to render word for word, but preserved the general style and force of the expression.	And in so doing, I did not hold it necessary to render word for word, but I preserved the general style and force of the language.

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No.	Query ID	Source ID	Query	Source	Query Translation	Source Translation
9	lact. inst. 4.15.21	verg. aen. 10.763	cumque iam medium fretum tenerent, tum pedibus mare ingressus consecutus est eos tamquam in solido gradiens, non ut poetae Orionem mentiuntur in pelago incedentem, qui demersa corporis parte umero supereminet undas .	Quam magnus Orion, cum pedes incedit medii per maxima Nerei stagna viam scindens, umero supereminet undas aut summis referens annosam montibus ornum ingrediturque solo et caput inter nubila condit:	And when they were already holding their course in the middle of the sea, he, walking with his feet upon the water, followed them, as though he were stepping on solid ground, not as the poets deceitfully tell us that Orion walks upon the sea who, though part of his body is submerged, towers above the waves with his shoulders .	Great as Orion, when cleaving a path he stalks on foot through the vast pools of mid-ocean, towers with his shoulder above the waves , or, carrying off an aged ash from mountain heights, walks the ground with head hidden in the clouds:
10	lact. inst. 1.13.12	verg. georg. 2.536	item noster Maro: aureus hanc uitam in terris Saturnus agebat .	Ante etiam sceptrum Dictaei regis et ante inopia quam caesis gens est epulata iuvenis, aureus hanc vitam in terris Saturnus agebat ; necdum etiam audierant inflari classica, necdum inpositos duris crepitare incudibus enses.	Likewise our Maro says: Golden Saturn lived this life on earth ;	Nay, before the Cretan king held sceptre, and before a godless race banqueted on slaughtered bullocks, such was the life golden Saturn lived on earth , while yet none had heard the clarion blare, none the sword blades ring, as they were laid on the stubborn anvil.

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No.	Query ID	Source ID	Query	Source	Query Translation	Source Translation
11	lact. inst. 7.3.13	lucr. 5.156	nam Lucretius cum mundum diceret non esse a diis constitutum, sic ait: dicere porro hominum causa uoluisse parare praeclaram mundi naturam deinde intulit desipere est.	Dicere porro hominum causa uoluisse parare praeclaram mundi naturam proptereaque allaudabile opus diuom laudare decere aeternumque putare atque immortale futurum, nec fas esse, deum quod sit ratione vetusta gentibus humanis fundatum perpetuo aevo, sollicitare suis ulla vi ex sedibus umquam nec verbis vexare et ab imo evertere summa, cetera de genere hoc affingere et addere, Memmi, desiperest.	For Lucretius, when he said that the world was not created by the gods, spoke as follows: Moreover, to say, that it was for the sake of men that they wished to prepare the wonderful nature of the world. And then he added: That is foolish.	To say further that for men’s sake they had the will to prepare the glorious structure of the world, and that therefore it is fitting to praise it as an admirable work of the gods; and to think that it will be everlasting and immortal, and that a thing which has by ancient contrivance of the gods been established for the races of mankind to all eternity may not ever lawfully be shaken from its foundations by any force, nor assailed by argument and overthrown from top to bottom; to feign this and other such conceits, one upon another, Memmius, is the act of a fool.

Case	Original	Content words	Function words	Citation	Morph num	Morph tense	Morph mood	Morph case	Morph all	Paraphrase 1	Paraphrase 2	Reorder	Random
1	0.63	0.62	0.6	0.62	0.63	0.64	0.64	0.63	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.63	0.51
2	0.81	0.79	0.43	0.78	0.77	0.81	0.81	0.77	0.77	0.82	0.79	0.75	0.49
3	0.76	0.74	0.61	0.7	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.52
4	0.9	0.88	0.73	1	0.88	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.56
5	0.72	0.72	0.56	0.63	0.71	0.72	0.72	0.7	0.7	0.71	0.7	0.7	0.29
6	0.87	0.86	0.49	0.77	0.85	0.86	0.86	0.86	0.85	0.86	0.82	0.84	0.38
7	0.45	0.46	0.53	0.53	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.47	0.47	0.46	0.45	0.45	0.58
8	0.95	0.93	0.69	0.95	0.9	0.9	0.83	0.83	0.9	0.86	0.65	0.7	0.56
9	0.83	0.84	0.47	0.78	0.82	0.82	0.81	0.83	0.82	0.83	0.82	0.83	0.46
10	0.66	0.67	0.53	0.64	0.62	0.61	0.66	0.63	0.61	0.66	0.55	0.56	0.48
11	0.75	0.79	0.49	0.78	0.73	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.76	0.72	0.69	0.39
Median Δ	0.0	0.01	0.17	0.02	0.02	0.0	0.0	0.01	0.02	0.0	0.02	0.02	0.34

Table 2: Cosine similarities under controlled modifications

Historical Languages and AI (Berlin, Germany)

First Steps towards a Tailored LLM for Ancient Scientific Texts (and beyond)

Workshop proposal

Organisers: Premshay Hermon; Orly Lewis; Gideon Manelis; Gabriele Torcoletti

Recent advances in digital classics as well as foundation LLMs have greatly improved the application of AI tools for the analysis of texts in ancient Greek. While AI Chat Interfaces allow scholars and students with no coding to perform advanced analysis, these interfaces notoriously suffer from hallucinations and limited training on ancient languages and on scholarly approaches and standards. A promising path forward is adopting the approach of ‘small LLMs’, which are gaining popularity in the commercial and industry worlds. These are LLMs tailored for particular fields or platforms.

The aim of the proposed workshop is to make first collaborative steps towards building an LLM trained specifically for the advanced scholarly analysis of Greco-Roman literature, through the case of scientific and technical texts. The ultimate goal is to build an LLM which can identify and analyse not only lexical and linguistic data, but also more complex philological, narratological, and stylistic layers of ancient texts, and integrate the analysis of the text in the original ancient language with information from manuscripts, scientific editions, commentaries and research literature.

Large language models (LLMs) are advanced AI systems that implement a probabilistic model. They are trained on extensive text corpora to predict and generate language by learning patterns of words, concepts, and relationships. They create internal representations that support flexible reasoning and text generation. Fine-tuning these models with carefully curated question-answer pairs from specific domains like ancient texts allows the models to specialize in recognizing historical languages, terminology, and scholarly inquiry styles. Small LLMs with fewer parameters can be effectively fine-tuned to perform specific tasks with less computational cost, making them accessible for humanistic research. This process improves the models' accuracy and relevance by focusing their capabilities on domain-specific knowledge, producing reliable tools that assist scholars in analyzing and interpreting classical literature.

The planned LLM would help in tasks ranging from identifying structural formulae in an ancient text or corpus, building an apparatus criticus, identifying figurative constructions and logical and rhetorical means, analysing the structure of an argument, identifying contradictions or digressions in an argument, and much more.

The workshop will focus on a key and early step in building a tailored LLM, namely creating a suitable dataset for training it. Such a dataset consists of a large number of human-

formulated questions and answers related to given data (e.g. an edition, a commentary, or a cluster of editions). These are then used to train the LLM to perform required tasks. Our aim is to create a dataset also for agentic AI. This means a dataset which performs agentic workflows for extracting and analysing relevant data from, *inter alia*, digital web-based editions, commentaries and other language platforms.

For the sake of feasibility and efficiency, we will focus on sources related to ancient medical and philosophical texts in Greek and Latin. However, we perceive this workshop as a case study and model for broader LLMs for all Greco-Roman literature, or for other historical languages and scholarly fields relying on them.

At the core of the workshop stand the questions and answers that participants will compose concerning the ancient texts. We will provide templates and guidelines for writing suitable questions and answers for training the LLM. Questions will pertain to content, style and terminology of ancient texts in Latin and ancient Greek. While the emphasis will be investigating these broad themes in ancient scientific and philosophical texts, the workshop will be open to those interested in ancient texts from any domain. Direct access to the ancient texts is not strictly necessary, but participants may want to consult some texts to fine-tune their questions and answers. We will provide key ancient sources – Galen, Hippocrates, Aristotle, Cicero, Lucretius, Seneca – in a searchable format, and participants may bring their own files for other texts.

Structure of the Workshop

- 1) A brief Introduction to LLMs. The basics of how LLMs work and explaining the significance of the task undertaken in the workshop.
- 2) Explanation of the work process during the workshop and showing examples and templates of the intended outcomes.
- 3) Hands-on work: writing Questions and answers using the templates. We plan several clusters, working on different kinds of sources: Greek medical texts, Latin medical Texts, Greek philosophical texts.

The perceived outcomes of the workshop:

- 1) A preliminary set of questions and answers (made available on a public repository).
- 2) A better and diverse understanding of kinds of questions and tasks scholars require.
- 3) Engaging scholars and students who are less AI-oriented in advancing AI capabilities in classics.
- 4) Concrete foundations for an active and collaborative community working towards small LLM(s) for classical scholarship.
- 5) Ultimately, this work will lead to the collaborative development of the tailored LLM.

We will promote the workshop through mailing lists (e.g. Digital Classics, Liverpool Classicists, Med-Med), as well as dedicated mailing groups of colleagues from the fields of history of medicine and digital classics, and relevant social media (Linkedin, Academia.edu).

Specific requirements:

- It would be best to hold the workshop in a computer room/lab. Otherwise, participants should bring the laptop.
- Good internet/WiFi connection.
- Screen and projector to show a presentation and shared work during the hands-on session.
- No technical skills or knowledge is required of participants.

Bios

Premshay Hermon is a Product manager and entrepreneur, specializing in VR and AI. He heads Atlomy's product and data-science work: the design and development of the Atlas and database and the development and testing of machine-learning models. He holds an M.A. (summa cum laude) from the Interdisciplinary Program in the Arts, Tel-Aviv University.

Orly Lewis is Associate Professor of Classics at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem. She focuses on Greco-Roman medicine and the history of scientific method. Her ERC project (ATLOMY) applies an interdisciplinary method for studying ancient medicine, combining philology with visual arts, experimental re-enactments, AI and software development. With her team she has developed advanced digital tools and platforms (e.g. atlas of historical anatomy; multimodal portal on ancient dissections; AI tool for composing detailed lexical entries on ancient terminology). During 2025-2026 academic year she will be a visiting professor at the Cote d'Azur University (France) in the CEPAM CNRS lab.

Gideon Manelis is a PhD candidate in Classics at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem. He is a research fellow in the ERC-funded ATLOMY project, a graduate of the Digital Humanities programme for M.A. students and a recipient of scholarships from the Mandel School for Advanced Studies in the Humanities and the Edelstein Centre for History and Philosophy of Science and Medicine. His research focuses on ancient medicine and Galen's theory of voice production, with interests in ancient anatomical and physiological studies and experimental reconstructions of ancient voice theories through digital interfaces.

Gabriele Torcoletti is a PhD candidate in Classical Studies at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem, within the MSCA Doctoral Network MECANO. The Network investigates the mechanisms of canonicity with a focus on digital tools and applications. His research explores

the reception of fragmentary Hellenistic physicians in Galen's works on the pulse. As part of his project, he is designing an interactive digital interface to map ancient medical ideas and terminology, with a focus on visualizing the pulse and its physiology.

PathFinder.AI

Detecting Migration and Mobility in Antique Latin Sources

Abstract

Migration has dominated the headlines for decades and is likely to remain so. Migration is essential to understand dynamics of present day and the Roman world alike (Purcell and Peregrine Horden. 2000; Tacoma. 2016). Yet, migrants are difficult to spot in the historical record (Cascio. 2017; Rapp) and sources are scarce for the classical period (Noy. 2000; Ricci. 2006; Collar. 2013; Handl. 2020; Handl. 2025). While the latter limitation can be mitigated by tapping into the rich corpus of so far understudied Christian writings, the massive corpus demolish any illusion that traditional, human-driven approach suffice in processing. This raises the fundamental question: To what extent can large-language-models (LLMs) accurately extract mobility patterns from Latin corpora, revolutionising our understanding of migration's role in Late Antiquity, through a novel Latin-specialized 'AI' workflow combining NER, contextual prompting, and entity linking? The proposed workflow employs a hybrid strategy. First, a generalist deep learning model for 'Named-Entity Recognition' (NER) will be trained on Latin texts. Second, a generative AI (e.g. GPT) will be prompted for movement semantics. And third, relation extraction (RE) will be used for trajectory reconstruction. Due to the lack of tagged historical mobility data, a new dataset will be created by annotating texts e.g. from Augustine of Hippo's (354-430 CE) corpus. PathFinder.AI aims thus to expand massively the available data on ancient migration and mobility and to

revolutionise historical research on the subject.

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Computational Approaches to Latin Semantics: Introducing the COALA Project

Anonymous ACL submission

Abstract

The ERC-selected COALA project (Computational Corpus Annotation for Quantitative Analysis of Latin Lexical Semantics) aims to model diachronic semantics in a low-resource historical language with both breadth and depth. Historical semantics theories remain under-tested against large-scale data (Adams, 2013; Traugott and Dasher, 2001), while computational approaches offer scalability but often lack sophistication, particularly regarding linguistic variation (Tahmasebi et al., 2021). COALA employs historical linguistic analysis and computational techniques to explore meaning variation over 2000 years of history of the Latin language. We are compiling a large diachronic Latin corpus, enriched with contextual sense annotation, drawing on established resources such as Latin WordNet (Biagetti et al., 2021) and building on previous work on Latin sense annotation (McGillivray et al., 2022; Marongiu and McGillivray, 2023). The manual annotation will be scaled up with Latin Word Sense Disambiguation algorithms advancing the state of the art (Bamman and Burns, 2020; Lendvai and Wick, 2022; Ghinassi et al., 2024). The project relies on two coordinated work-streams to ensure both quality and scalability: a curated stream, led by Latin linguists, focuses on annotation reliability, while a computational stream, led by computational linguists, develops scalable automatic methods. Together, these streams provide a robust interdisciplinary framework that advances historical semantics, strengthens resources for Latin as a low-resource language, and demonstrates the broader potential of AI to transform the study of historical languages, enabling a more systematic evaluation of semantic change theories.

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Technical Standards for Latin and Ancient Greek (TESLA): Referencing, Evaluation, Documentation

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The rapid expansion of digital methods for Latin and Ancient Greek — ranging from large language models to corpus-driven linguistic analysis — has outpaced the development and adoption of shared technical standards (Filogrosso et al. 2025). Existing robust solutions for text referencing, model evaluation, and resource documentation remain fragmented and unevenly adopted across the field. This contribution asks: how can the community of Digital Classics coordinate around interoperable technical standards that ensure reproducibility, comparability, and long-term sustainability for computational work on Latin and Ancient Greek texts?

Without stable and widely accepted standards, digital resources risk becoming isolated, opaque, or irreproducible, limiting their reuse and scholarly impact. Existing frameworks — such as Canonical Text Services (Tiepmar et al. 2014), CITE architecture (Koentges et al. 2021), Hugging Face¹, model cards (Mitchell et al. 2019), datasheets (Geburu et al. 2021) — are rarely aligned with one another or adapted systematically to the specific challenges of historical languages, including textual variance, editorial uncertainty, and complex linguistic annotation.

This pitch proposes the creation of TESLA, an international working group or special interest group dedicated to reinforcing, adapting, and extending technical standards for the digital processing of Latin and Ancient Greek. The proposed methodology is collaborative and incremental: (1) surveying current practices; (2) identifying gaps and mismatches between existing standards; (3) developing concrete guidelines, reference implementations, and best-practice recommendations; and (4) fostering adoption through workshops, shared repositories, and community-driven evaluation benchmarks.

Such innovations aim at providing useful standards in various areas, such as

- lemmatization, where comprehensive lists of all existing lemmata are still missing (Mambrini and Passarotti 2019);
- named entity recognition, where standard annotation classes like *person* and *location* are often not well-defined for ancient literary contexts (Beersmans et al. 2023; Yousef et al. 2023);
- encoding, where divergent digital representations of diacritics negatively impact searchability and interoperability of text editions (Celano 2024).

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¹ <https://huggingface.co/>

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